

LAFP: Logic-based Argumentation Framework with Preferences ^{*}

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Abstract. Explaining query answers in inconsistent knowledge bases (KBs) has been a prominent problem in AI, especially in Semantic Web. However, in the context of inconsistent KBs, particularly when the data comes with preferences, the problem of explaining query answers remains a challenge, for instance, the explanation can not be exhaustive and user-friendly. We aim to provide a generic and unifying framework in which we use argumentation as an explanation tool. To do so, we first translate inconsistent prioritized KBs to argumentation frameworks (AFs). We then investigate how the AF can provide persuasion dialogues constructed from argumentation-based explanations. As an initial step of our work, the translation of prioritized KBs into AFs is crucial before providing persuasion dialogues. This work has been studied in our submitted paper. Therefore, we place ourselves to explore the problem of translation of inconsistent prioritized KBs into AFs. We propose a novel logic-based argumentation framework with preferences (LAFP). We also provide a theoretical analysis of the LAFP with respect to its syntax and its properties. Finally, we empirically study the applicability of our proposed framework in real-data applications. The experimental results indicate that the proposed one provides more comprehensive explanations for query answers. It is worth mentioning that this paper is a technical report of our pre-release version, and we will report our specific evaluation for the experiment in future versions.

Keywords: Inconsistency-tolerant reasoning · Argumentation · Explanation.

1 Introduction

Explainability has recently started to play a prominent role in different areas of AI, especially in Semantic Web. Explaining ontological query answers allows users to understand not only what is or is not entailed by a knowledge base under semantics, but also why. It has recently been investigated in the context of an Ontology-Based Data Access (OBDA), namely existential rules (Datalog[±]) and description logics (DLs) [13,14,7,8,3,2,4,12,7]. In the OBDA context, a prominent approach is identifying explanations as minimal sets of facts (that could

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be responsible for the derived conclusion w.r.t. inconsistent KBs) [13,14], which are called *causes* in the DL context [9,8]. The explanation of these approaches can be less meaningful (i.e., not providing complete information for the explanations), in particular when data comes with preferences (We refer the reader to a motivation example in our submitted paper to see in detail). Another approach is based on an abstract argumentation [3,2,4,12,7]. Bienvenu [7] worked on prioritized KB expressed by the DLs of DL-Lite family. The authors clarified the relationship between optimal repairs and different notions of extensions for (set-based) argumentation frameworks, although the issue of explanation has not been studied. Arioua et.al studied the problem of explaining query entailment under ICR semantics (ICR for "intersection of closed repairs") in the Datalog[±] [3,2,4]. Their definition of explanation is based on abstract argumentation for explaining positive and negative answers under the ICR semantics. However, the generating arguments from KB are exponential, and they do not consider the presence of priority relation over facts. The closest related work is by Ho et.al [12] who introduce a prioritized argumentation framework to explain query answers under AR and BAR semantics (AR for "All ABox repair" and BAR for "Brave"). Note that the priority relation in [12] is only applied to the case of totally preordered fact bases. They also provide the definition of explanation as a pair of dialectical trees for and against the query answer. However, such explanations might consist of many arguments, and users are expected to understand argumentation and dialectical trees.

Throughout existing literature, it can be seen that the problem of explaining query answers remains a challenge. We aim to provide a generic and unifying framework in which we use argumentation as an explanation tool. To do so, we first translate inconsistent prioritized KBs to argumentation frameworks (AFs). We then investigate how the AF can provide persuasion dialogues constructed from argumentation-based explanations. As an initial step of our work, the translation of prioritized KBs into AFs is crucial before providing persuasion dialogues to users. This work has been studied in our submitted paper. In this paper, therefore, we aim to investigate the problem of translation of inconsistent prioritized KBs into AFs. We propose a novel logic-based argumentation framework with preferences (LAFP). The novel LAFP can reduce the huge number of arguments, which is formally compared to the existing argumentation-based approach [12,2]. We also provide a theoretical analysis of the LAFP with respect to its syntax and its properties. Finally, we empirically study the applicability of our proposed framework in real-data applications. The experimental results indicate that the proposed one provides more comprehensive explanations for query answers. This paper is a technical report of our pre-release version, and we will report our specific evaluation for the experiment in future versions.

2 Preliminaries

2.1 Datalog[±]

According to [10], Datalog[±] (also known as existential rules) is a natural and general framework to express several specific knowledge representation languages adapted to query answering, such as RDFS (the basic semantic web language), constraints in F-logic-Lite (a subset of F-logic, a formalism for object-oriented deductive databases), and the description logics (DL) of the DL-Lite family tailored for conjunctive query answering. In this paper, our goal aims to explain query answering where data is extracted from web pages or integrated from different databases. Therefore, we consider Datalog[±] as the first step of our framework to model data and tractable query answering. Next, we introduce notation and terminology for talking about Datalog[±] KBs [10], then recall different inconsistency-tolerant semantics.

Datalog[±] Knowledge Bases. We assume a set C of *constants*, a set V of *variables*, and a set N of *labeled nulls*. A *term* t is a constant, null, or variable. Assume that a set of predicates, each associated with an arity, i.e., a non-negative integer. An *atom* has the form $p(t_1, \dots, t_n)$, where p is an n -ary predicate, and t_1, \dots, t_n are terms. An *instance* I is a finite set of atom $p(t)$, where t is a tuple of constants and nulls. In Datalog[±], a conjunction of atoms or an atom in I is also called a *fact*. A *database* \mathcal{F} is a finite instance without nulls. A *homomorphism* is a substitution $H : C \cup N \cup V \rightarrow C \cup N \cup V$ that is the identity on C and maps N to $C \cup N$. With a slight abuse of notation, homomorphisms are applied also to (sets/conjunctions of) atoms. A conjunctive query (CQ) Q has the form $\phi(x_1, \dots, x_n)$ where $\phi(x_1, \dots, x_n)$ is a conjunction of atoms without null. The answer to Q over an instance \mathcal{F} , denoted $Q(I)$, is the set of all tuples (c_1, \dots, c_n) over C for which there is a homomorphism h s.t. $h(\phi(x_1, \dots, x_n)) \subseteq I$ and $h(x_i) = c_i$. If $n = 0$, then Q is a Boolean conjunctive query (BCQ).

A set of Datalog[±] rules is a set of *tuple-generating dependencies* (TGDs). TGDs are called *existential rules* (or simply called *rules*). A TGD σ is a first-order implication $\forall x \phi(x) \rightarrow \exists z \psi(y, z)$, where z, y, z are variables, $\phi(x)$ (the *body*) and $\psi(y, z)$ (the *head*) are conjunctions of atoms. A TGD σ is satisfied by \mathcal{F} , written by $\mathcal{F} \models \sigma$ if whenever there is a homomorphism h s.t. $h(\phi(x)) \subseteq \mathcal{F}$, there exists an *extension* h' of h (i.e., $h \subseteq h'$) s.t. $h'(\psi(y, z)) \subseteq \mathcal{F}$. A *negative constraint* (NC) is a rule of the form $\forall x \phi(x) \rightarrow \perp$ where $\phi(x)$ is a conjunction of atoms, and \perp denotes the truth constant false. An *equality-generating dependency* (EGD) is a rule of the form $\forall x \phi(x, y) \rightarrow x = y$ where $\phi(x, y)$ is a conjunction of atoms. An EGD is satisfied by \mathcal{F} if whenever there is a homomorphism h s.t. $h(\phi(x, y)) \subseteq \mathcal{F}$, then $h(x) = h(y)$. Finite sets of NCs and EGDs are also called *constraints*.

A *knowledge base* (KB) $\mathcal{K} = (\mathcal{F}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{C})$ is a tuple of sets of facts, rules and constraints, respectively. For a KB $\mathcal{K} = (\mathcal{F}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{C})$, the closure $\text{Cl}_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{F})$ is the set of all ground atoms, built from constants in \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{R} , entailed by \mathcal{F} and the TGDs of \mathcal{R} . $\text{Cl}_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{F})$ is finite. A (BCQ) Q on \mathcal{K} can be answered by calculating the chase and checking whether the query is entailed by the models of \mathcal{F}, \mathcal{R} . In

this case, we write $\text{Cl}_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{F}) \models Q$. Given a KB $\mathcal{K} = (\mathcal{F}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{C})$, a set of facts \mathcal{F} is *inconsistent* with respect to a set of rules \mathcal{R} and constraints \mathcal{C} (or \mathcal{R} -inconsistent for short) iff (1) there exists an NC constraint $C \in \mathcal{C}$ such that $\text{Cl}_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{F}) \models \perp$, or (2) there is an EGD constraint C which is violated¹. Accordingly, \mathcal{F} is said to be \mathcal{R} -consistent if it is not inconsistent. Moreover, \mathcal{K} is said to be inconsistent iff there exists a set of facts $\mathcal{F}' \subseteq \mathcal{F}$ s.t. \mathcal{F}' is \mathcal{R} -inconsistent. Next, we define a *conflict* of a KB as a minimal \mathcal{R} -inconsistent subset of \mathcal{F} . We denote the set of all conflicts of \mathcal{K} by $\text{Conflicts}(\mathcal{K})$. Observe that if \mathcal{K} is inconsistent, then every candidate answer to Q is uninformative and motivates the need for alternative inconsistency-tolerant semantics.

Repairs. To extract meaningful information from an inconsistent KB, it is useful to consider the parts of the data that are consistent with the theory. This can be formalized using the notion of repair:

Definition 1. (*Repairs*) Let $\mathcal{K} = (\mathcal{F}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{C})$ be a flat Datalog[±] KB. A repair \mathcal{B} of \mathcal{K} is an inclusion-maximal subset of \mathcal{F} such that $\text{Cl}_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{B})$ is \mathcal{R} -consistent. We denote the set of all repairs w.r.t. \mathcal{F} by $\text{Repairs}(\mathcal{K})$.

Repairs treats all facts equally. However, preferences between conflicting facts should be considered when they are available. According to ([15,7,8]), we introduce definitions in the prioritized setting. Note that if the facts over \mathcal{F} have the same priority, then the knowledge base is flat.

Definition 2. (*Priority relation*) Given a Datalog[±] KB $\mathcal{K} = (\mathcal{F}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{C})$, a priority relation $>$ for \mathcal{K} is preorder relation over the facts of \mathcal{F} . The relation $>$ is total if $\forall \alpha, \beta, \{\alpha, \beta\} \in \mathcal{F}$, then $\alpha > \beta$ or $\beta > \alpha$.

Definition 3. (*Prioritized Datalog[±] KB*) A prioritized Datalog[±] KB is a pair $(\mathcal{K}, >)$ including the KB \mathcal{K} and priority relation $>$ over the facts of \mathcal{F} . We refer to the notation $\mathcal{K}_{>}$ as shorthand for $(\mathcal{K}, >)$,

Next, we define two notions of *globally-optimal repairs* (GP) and *completion-optimal repairs* (CP), which is inspired by [15,8].

Definition 4. (*Preferred Repairs*) Given a prioritized Datalog[±] KB $\mathcal{K}_{>}$ with $(\mathcal{F}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{C})$. Let $\mathcal{B}_1, \mathcal{B}_2$ be two repairs in $\text{Repairs}(\mathcal{K})$, \mathcal{B}_1 is preferred to \mathcal{B}_2 , denoted by $\mathcal{B}_1 \succeq_{\star} \mathcal{B}_2$ where $\star \in \{GP, CP\}$, which is defined in two different ways:

1. $\mathcal{B}_1 \succeq_{GP} \mathcal{B}_2$ iff $\forall \beta \in \mathcal{B}_2 \setminus \mathcal{B}_1, \exists \alpha \in \mathcal{B}_1 \setminus \mathcal{B}_2, \alpha > \beta$.
2. $\mathcal{B}_1 \succeq_{CP} \mathcal{B}_2$ iff $\mathcal{B}_1 \succeq_{GP} \mathcal{B}_2$ for $>$ is total.

We denote the set of preferred repairs w.r.t. $\mathcal{K}_{>}$ as $\text{Repairs}(\mathcal{K}, >_{\star}) = \{\mathcal{B} \in \text{Repairs}(\mathcal{K}) \mid \text{there is no } \mathcal{B}' \in \text{Repairs}(\mathcal{K}) \text{ s.t. } \mathcal{B}' >_{\star} \mathcal{B}\}$.

¹ An EGD is violated in \mathcal{F} when we apply the TGDs to \mathcal{F} . In the paper, we restrict EGDs to binary ones; that is, those which body $\forall x\phi(x)$ is the conjunction of exactly two atoms, e.g., $p(x, y) \wedge q(x, z) \rightarrow y = z$.

Remark 1. The relation \geq_* is pre-order, that is: *reflexive* ($\mathcal{B}_1 \geq_* \mathcal{B}_1$), *transitive* (if $\mathcal{B}_1 \geq_* \mathcal{B}_2$ and $\mathcal{B}_2 \geq_* \mathcal{B}_3$ then $\mathcal{B}_1 \geq_* \mathcal{B}_3$). A *strict pre-order* $>_*$ is an irreflexive ($\mathcal{B}_1 \geq_* \mathcal{B}_1$ does not hold) and transitive binary relation. $\mathcal{B}_1 >_* \mathcal{B}_2$ means that \mathcal{B}_1 is strictly preferred to \mathcal{B}_2 . A strict pre-order is generally defined from \geq_* as $\mathcal{B}_1 >_* \mathcal{B}_2$ iff $\mathcal{B}_1 \geq_* \mathcal{B}_2$ and $\mathcal{B}_2 \not\geq_* \mathcal{B}_1$. \mathcal{B}_1 is equal to \mathcal{B}_2 , denoted by $\mathcal{B}_1 =_* \mathcal{B}_2$, iff $\mathcal{B}_1 \geq_* \mathcal{B}_2$ and $\mathcal{B}_2 \geq_* \mathcal{B}_1$.

Repair-based semantics. We next recall three prominent inconsistency-tolerant semantics (brave, AR and IAR), which we parameterize by the considered type of repair:

Definition 5. (*AR $_{\geq}$, BAR $_{\geq}$ and IAR $_{\geq}$ semantics*) Let $\mathcal{K}_{>}$ be a prioritized Datalog $^{\pm}$ KB with $(\mathcal{F}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{C})$ and Q be a query. For $\star \in \{GP, CP\}$, then:

- Q is entailed by $\mathcal{K}_{>}$ under AR $_{\geq}$ semantics, written $\mathcal{K}_{>} \models_{AR} Q$ iff for every preferred repair $\mathcal{B} \in \text{Repairs}(\mathcal{K}, >_*)$, $\text{Cl}_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{B}) \models Q$.
- Q is entailed by $\mathcal{K}_{>}$ under BAR $_{\geq}$ semantics, written $\mathcal{K}_{>} \models_{BAR} Q$ iff for some preferred repairs $\mathcal{B} \in \text{Repairs}(\mathcal{K}, >_*)$, $\text{Cl}_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{B}) \models Q$.
- Q is entailed by $\mathcal{K}_{>}$ under IAR $_{\geq}$ semantics, written $\mathcal{K}_{>} \models_{IAR} Q$ iff for $\mathcal{B} = \bigcap \{R \mid R \in \text{Repairs}(\mathcal{K}, >_*)\}$, $\text{Cl}_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{B}) \models Q$

The AR semantics require that a query is entailed from all preferred repairs. The BAR semantics require a query that is entailed by some preferred repairs. Throughout the paper, we will refer to the accepted answers under AR semantics (resp. the accepted answers under BAR semantics) as certain answers (resp. possible answers). In our context, the accepted query has either a *yes*-answer (entailed) or a *no*-answer (not entailed). These semantics are related as follows: $\mathcal{K}_{>} \models_{IAR} Q \Rightarrow \mathcal{K}_{>} \models_{AR} Q \Rightarrow \mathcal{K}_{>} \models_{BAR} Q$

Example 1. We utilize the inconsistent KB about the university domain. We model it by using Datalog $^{\pm}$ as follows: Let $\mathcal{K}_{>}^1 = \{\mathcal{R}_1, \mathcal{C}_1, \mathcal{F}_1\}$ be the inconsistent KB, where

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{R}_1 &= \{\text{AProf}(X) \rightarrow \text{Prof}(X), \text{Advice}(X, Y) \rightarrow \text{Prof}(X), \\ &\quad \text{FProf}(X) \rightarrow \text{Prof}(X)\} \\ \mathcal{C}_1 &= \{\text{AProf}(X), \text{FProf}(X) \rightarrow \perp, \text{Prof}(X), \text{Postdoc}(X) \rightarrow \perp, \\ &\quad \text{Lecturer}(X), \text{Postdoc}(X) \rightarrow \perp\} \\ \mathcal{F}_1 &= \{\text{Postdoc}(\text{ann}), \text{AProf}(\text{ann}), \text{FProf}(\text{ann}), \text{Advice}(\text{ann}, \text{bob}), \\ &\quad \text{Teach}(\text{ann}, c_1)\} \end{aligned}$$

The conflict among facts is displayed below. An arrow from α to β indicates that $\alpha > \beta$ while a line indicates that $\alpha = \beta$.

The KB admits the repairs R_1, R_2, R_3 when not considering the priority over facts. Each repair includes one of the assertions about the position \mathbf{ann} occupies (Postdoc or AProf or FProf), and excludes all conflicting assertions. For example, the repair R_3 contains $\text{Postdoc}(\mathbf{ann})$ and eliminates the three assertions that conflict with it, namely, $\text{AProf}(\mathbf{ann})$, $\text{FProf}(\mathbf{ann})$, and $\text{Advice}(\mathbf{ann}, \mathbf{bob})$.

$$\begin{aligned} R_1 &= \{\text{Lecturer}(\mathbf{ann}), \text{AProf}(\mathbf{ann}), \text{Advice}(\mathbf{ann}, \mathbf{bob}), \text{Teach}(\mathbf{ann}, c_1)\} \\ R_2 &= \{\text{Lecturer}(\mathbf{ann}), \text{FProf}(\mathbf{ann}), \text{Advice}(\mathbf{ann}, \mathbf{bob}), \text{Teach}(\mathbf{ann}, c_1)\} \\ R_3 &= \{\text{Postdoc}(\mathbf{ann}), \text{Teach}(\mathbf{ann}, c_1)\} \end{aligned}$$

In the case of priority relation, we observe that $\text{Repairs}(\mathcal{K}, >_*) = \{R_1, R_2\}$.

Recall that $Q_1(\mathbf{ann}) = \text{Prof}(\mathbf{ann})$. The query asks whether there is someone who is a professor. An answer "*ann is a professor*" is a certain answer, i.e. $\mathcal{K}_{>} \models_{\text{AR}} \text{Prof}(\mathbf{ann})$, since $Q_1(\mathbf{ann})$ is accepted in all preferred repairs.

Consider a query $Q_2(\mathbf{ann}) = \text{Lecturer}(\mathbf{ann})$ asking whether a person \mathbf{ann} is a lecturer. We observe that for all repairs,

$$\text{Cl}_{\mathcal{R}}(\bigcap_{R \in \text{Repairs}(\mathcal{K}, >_*)} R) \models Q_2(\mathbf{ann}). \text{ Thus, } \mathcal{K}_{>} \models_{\text{IAR}} Q_2(\mathbf{ann}).$$

A query $Q_3(\mathbf{ann}) = \text{AProf}(\mathbf{ann})$ asks whether a person \mathbf{ann} is an associate professor. It holds that $\mathcal{K}_{>} \not\models_{\text{BAR}} Q_3(\mathbf{ann})$ (since $\text{Cl}_{\mathcal{R}}(R_2) \not\models Q_3(\mathbf{ann})$ and $\text{Cl}_{\mathcal{R}}(R_1) \models Q_3(\mathbf{ann})$), whereas it is not an answer under the AR semantic. It follows that the answer is accepted only in some preferred repairs. In other words, "*ann is an associate professor*" is a possible answer.

2.2 Argumentation Frameworks (AF)

In preparation for the following section, we recall the basics of argumentation frameworks and related definitions.

Definition 6. *An abstract argumentation framework is a pair $\mathcal{AF} = (\text{Arg}, \text{Att})$ where Arg is a set of arguments and $\text{Att} \subseteq \text{Arg} \times \text{Arg}$ is the attack relation. When $(A, B) \in \text{Att}$, we say A attacks B .*

Argumentation semantics are usually based upon *extensions* defined as sets of coherent arguments. These extensions consist of *admissible*, *complete*, *stable*, *preferred* and *grounded semantics*. We recall some notions of extension.

Definition 7. *Let $\mathcal{S} \subseteq \text{Arg}$ be a set of arguments and $A, B \in \text{Arg}$. \mathcal{S} attacks an argument A if there exists an $B \in \mathcal{S}$ s.t. $(B, A) \in \text{Att}$. \mathcal{S} defends an argument A if \mathcal{S} attacks every argument attacking A . \mathcal{S} is conflict-free if there are no arguments $A, B \in \mathcal{S}$ s.t. $(A, B) \in \text{Def}_{>}$. \mathcal{S} is an admissible extension (**adm**) if \mathcal{S} is conflict-free and defends each argument in it. \mathcal{S} is a complete extension (**cmp**) if \mathcal{S} is an admissible extension containing all arguments that it defends. \mathcal{S} is a preferred extension (**prf**) if \mathcal{S} is a maximal (w.r.t. set inclusion) admissible extension. \mathcal{S} is a stable extension (**stb**) if \mathcal{S} is a conflict-free and attacks every argument which is not in it. \mathcal{S} is a grounded extension (**grd**) if \mathcal{S} is a minimal (w.r.t. set inclusion) complete extension.*

To determine the acceptability of arguments in terms of the extensions, the notions of acceptance are introduced: the *sceptical* and *credulous* acceptance. In particular, credulous acceptance clarifies whether an argument is accepted in at least one extension, and sceptical acceptance shows that an argument is accepted in all extensions.

Definition 8. (*Acceptance and rejection*) Let $\mathcal{AF} = (\text{Arg}, \text{Att})$ be an AF, $A \in \text{Arg}$ and $\text{sem} \in \{\text{stb}, \text{prf}, \text{cmp}, \text{grad}\}$. Then, A is sceptically accepted w.r.t. sem iff it is in all extensions under sem ; A is credulously accepted w.r.t. sem iff it is in at least one extension under sem ; A is rejected iff it is not in any extension under sem .

3 Logic-based argumentation framework with preferences

Now that the basic principles have been discussed, we are ready to examine how Argumentation can be applied to explaining inconsistency-tolerant query answering in Datalog[±] KBs. In general, the main idea of the argumentation-based approach is: we translate prioritized KBs into argumentation frameworks, and we compute argumentation-based explanations. Based on these explanations, we provide persuasion dialogues to allow users to understand why the querying answers are (not) accepted under the repairs.

In preparation for the following section, we first recall the Prioritized Argumentation Framework (PAF) provided by [12] and based on the original framework of [11]. This PAF has deductive arguments and defeat attacks where an argument A defeats an argument B if there is an element of the supports of B which is \mathcal{R} -inconsistent with the conclusion of A , and A is at least as preferred as B .

Definition 9. (*Prioritized Argumentation Framework $\mathcal{AF}'_{>_{pr}}$*) Let $\mathcal{K}_{>}$ be a prioritized Datalog[±] KB with $(\mathcal{F}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{C})$. A prioritized argumentation framework for \mathcal{K} is a triple $\mathcal{AF}'_{>_{pr}} = (\text{Arg}'_{>_{pr}}, \text{Def}'_{>_{pr}})$ with $\text{Def}'_{>_{pr}} \subseteq \text{Arg}'_{>_{pr}} \times \text{Arg}'_{>_{pr}}$, where:

- A (PAF) argument $A \in \text{Arg}'_{>_{pr}}$ is a tuple (Ψ, α) with Ψ a non-empty \mathcal{R} -consistent subset of \mathcal{F} and α a set of facts such that: (1) $\Psi \subseteq \mathcal{F}$ and $\text{Cl}_{\mathcal{R}}(\Psi)$ is \mathcal{R} -consistent ((consistency), (2) $\alpha \subseteq \text{Cl}_{\mathcal{R}}(\Psi)$ (entailment), and (3) $\nexists \Psi' \subset \Psi$ s.t. $\alpha \subseteq \text{Cl}_{\mathcal{R}}(\Psi')$ (minimality). We denote the support Ψ of an argument A by $\text{Sup}(A)$ and the conclusion α by $\text{Con}(A)$.
- A defeats B , denoted by $(A, B) \in \text{Def}'_{>_{pr}}$, iff $\exists \beta \in \text{Sup}(B)$ s.t. $\text{Cl}_{\mathcal{R}}(\{\text{Con}(A), \beta\})$ is \mathcal{R} -inconsistent, and $A >_{pr} B$.

The PAF $\mathcal{AF}'_{>_{pr}}$ generated from a prioritized KB has been proven to possess properties such as the correspondence between the set of preferred repair and the set of preferred (resp. stable) extensions, the desirable postulates and the equivalence results for query answering in the OBDA field [12].

However, one of the main drawbacks of this method is the huge number of arguments. Indeed, the authors in [16] proved that the number of arguments

is exponential w.r.t. the number of free-facts. Moreover, the priority relation in [12] is only applied to the case of totally preordered fact bases. In order to deal with the drawbacks, we introduce a novel LAFP, which efficiently generates arguments and defeats from an inconsistent prioritized KB. This LAFP $\mathcal{AF}_>$ possesses all of the desirable properties of the LAFP $\mathcal{AF}'_{>_{pr}}$.

3.1 New Argumentation Framework $\mathcal{AF}_>$

In this section, we introduce the novel LAFP $\mathcal{AF}_>$. The LAFP $\mathcal{AF}_>$ possesses arguments that are built upon other arguments and defeat attacks. In the novel LAFP setting, we lift the relation \geq_\star over preferred repairs of $\mathcal{K}_>$ to a prioritized relation on sets of arguments. In what follows, we shall write $A \geq_\star B$ to indicate that an argument A is at least as preferred as an argument B where $\star \in \{\text{GP}, \text{CP}\}$ (Example 2 illustrates two instances for \geq_\star). From now on, we shall use $>$ instead of $>_\star$ throughout the paper.

The LAFP $\mathcal{AF}_>$ considers a defeat attack as a variant of *undercut* attack in the case of the preferences, in which an argument A undercut attacks an argument B if there is an element of the support of B which is \mathcal{R} -inconsistent with the conclusion of A . Intuitively, the defeat attack succeeds if and only if the priority argument of higher level attacks the one of the lower level. This attack is not symmetric.

Note that the framework described in this section has some similarities with the ASPIC+ framework, but the ASPIC+ cannot be directly instantiated with Datalog[±] since this framework does not support the NCs and EGDs constraints for this language.²

Definition 10. (*Logic-based argumentation framework with preferences $\mathcal{AF}_>$*). Let $\mathcal{K}_>$ be a prioritized Datalog[±] KB with $(\mathcal{F}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{C})$. A prioritized argumentation framework for \mathcal{K} is a pair $\mathcal{AF}_> = (\text{Arg}_>, \text{Def}_>)$ with $\text{Def}_> \subseteq \text{Arg}_> \times \text{Arg}_>$, where:

- An argument $A \in \text{Arg}_>$ is either (1) a fact f where $f \in \mathcal{F}$ s.t. $\text{Con}(A) = f$ and $\text{Sup}(A) = f$, or (2) $A_1, \dots, A_n \rightarrow f'$ where $A_1, \dots, A_n \in \text{Arg}_>$ s.t. there exists a tuple (r, π) where $r \in \mathcal{R}$, π is a homomorphism from the body of r to $\{\text{Con}(A_1), \dots, \text{Con}(A_n)\}$ and f' is the resulting atom from the rule application. $\text{Con}(A) = f'$ and $\text{Sup}(A) = \text{Sup}(A_1) \cup \dots \cup \text{Sup}(A_n)$. (Note that in both cases, $\text{Sup}(A)$ must be \mathcal{R} -consistent).
- A defeats B , denoted by $(A, B) \in \text{Def}_>$, iff $\exists \beta \in \text{Sup}(B)$ s.t. $\text{Cl}_{\mathcal{R}}(\{\text{Con}(A), \beta\})$ is \mathcal{R} -inconsistent, and $A > B$.

With a slight abuse of notation, we also use the notations $\text{Con}(A)$ and $\text{Sup}(A)$ to refer to the conclusion of an argument and the support of an argument in LAFP.

² When instantiating ASPIC+, one usually has to add all the tautologies of the language in the set of rules to guarantee that the result will be consistent, i.e. to satisfy the rationality postulates defined by [1]. To avoid adding this huge number of rules and also with the goal of decreasing the number of arguments, we propose not to add them. However, the cost of forgetting to add those rules (and the arguments generated using them) would result in a violation of rationality postulates.

However, the conclusion is not a set anymore (see Definition 9). The reason is that \mathcal{K} can be processed w.l.o.g. to contain only rules with atomic head [6].

Note that, compared to the former PAF $\mathcal{AF}'_{>_{pr}}$, the novel LAFP can reduce the number of arguments. The reason is that, by Definition 9, the minimality property of the structure of arguments implies that the argument have excess facts in their support (See Example 1 in [17] for detail). To avoid this, one will remove the arguments that have the same support and their conclusions being able to be decomposed. Clearly, by Definition 10, we reconstruct the deductive argument from either the fact or from the argument whose atoms can be applied to the rules. With this new structure, the novel LAFP possesses less exponential arguments. Below, Corollary shows the difference between these two frameworks.

Corollary 1. *Given a prioritized Datalog[±] KB $\mathcal{K}_>$ with $(\mathcal{F}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{C})$, the corresponding novel LAFP $\mathcal{AF}_> = (\text{Arg}_>, \text{Def}_>)$, and the LAFP $\mathcal{AF}'_{>_{pr}} = (\text{Arg}'_{>_{pr}}, \text{Def}'_{>_{pr}})$. Then it holds that $|\text{Arg}'_{>_{pr}}| \geq |\text{Arg}_>|$.*

Once the structure of the $\mathcal{AF}_>$ is generated, we next clarify the relationship between preferred repairs and different notions of extensions for the novel $\mathcal{AF}_>$.

3.2 Preferred Repairs and LAFP Extensions

Proposition 1. *(Preferred & Stable Characterisation) Let $\mathcal{K}_>$ be a prioritized Datalog[±] KB with $(\mathcal{F}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{C})$, $\mathcal{AF}_> = (\text{Arg}_>, \text{Def}_>)$ be the LAFP corresponding and $\text{sem} \in \{\text{prf}, \text{stb}\}$. Then,*

$$\text{Exts}_{\text{sem}}(\mathcal{AF}_>) = \{\text{Args}(\mathcal{A}) \mid \mathcal{A} \in \text{Repairs}(\mathcal{K}, >_*)\}$$

Proposition 1 follows from the following lemma. Lemma 1 shows that a repair of the KB has a higher priority than any consistent subsets of facts of the KB.

Lemma 1. *Given a prioritized Datalog[±] KB $\mathcal{K}_> = (\mathcal{F}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{C})$, if $\mathcal{A} \in \text{Repairs}(\mathcal{K}, >_*)$ and $\mathcal{R}' \subseteq \mathcal{R}$ is a consistent set of facts, then $\mathcal{R}' \not\star_* \mathcal{A}$.*

Proof. We assume that \mathcal{R}' is consistent. Then, there exists a $\mathcal{R}'' \in \text{Repairs}(\mathcal{K})$ such that $\mathcal{R}' \subseteq \mathcal{R}''$. By the monotonic property of $>$, $\mathcal{R}'' > \mathcal{R}'$. Since $\mathcal{A} \in \text{Repairs}(\mathcal{K}, >_*)$, $\mathcal{R}'' \not\star \mathcal{A}$ and by the transitivity property of $>$, we infer that $\mathcal{R}' \not\star \mathcal{A}$.

Now we prove Proposition 1.

Proof. We separate the proof of Proposition 1 into two parts:

1. We prove $\{\text{Args}(\mathcal{A}) \mid \mathcal{A} \in \text{Repairs}(\mathcal{K}, >_*)\} \subseteq \text{Exts}_{\text{sem}}(\mathcal{AF}_>)$.
2. We prove $\text{Exts}_{\text{sem}}(\mathcal{AF}_>) \subseteq \{\text{Args}(\mathcal{A}) \mid \mathcal{A} \in \text{Repairs}(\mathcal{K}, >_*)\}$.
 1. We prove $\{\text{Args}(\mathcal{A}) \mid \mathcal{A} \in \text{Repairs}(\mathcal{K}, >_*)\} \subseteq \text{Exts}_{\text{sem}}(\mathcal{AF}_>)$. Suppose that $\mathcal{A} \in \text{Repairs}(\mathcal{K}, >_*)$ and $\mathcal{E} = \text{Args}(\mathcal{A})$, we show that \mathcal{E} is a stable extension of $\mathcal{AF}_>$, i.e., $\mathcal{E} \in \text{Exts}_{\text{sem}}(\mathcal{AF}_>)$. First, we prove that \mathcal{E} is conflict-free. Suppose for a contradiction that \mathcal{E} is not conflict-free. There exist two arguments $C, D \in \mathcal{E}$ s.t. $(C, D) \in \text{Def}_>$. From the definition of attack, there exists $\beta \in \text{Sup}(D)$

such that $\text{Cl}_{\mathcal{R}}(\{\text{Con}(C), \beta\})$ is \mathcal{R} -inconsistent. Hence, $\text{Cl}_{\mathcal{R}}(\text{Sup}(C) \cup \{\beta\})$ is \mathcal{R} -inconsistent. It follows that \mathcal{A} is not inconsistent which is a contradiction. Thus \mathcal{E} must be conflict-free.

Next, we prove that \mathcal{E} defeats all arguments not belonging to it. Let $C \in \text{Arg}_{>} \setminus \mathcal{E}$ and $\alpha \in \text{Sup}(C) \setminus \mathcal{A}$. Consider the argument $D : \mathcal{A} \rightarrow \wedge \mathcal{A}$. Clearly, $D \in \text{Arg}_{>}$. We show that D defeats C . Since $\alpha \notin \mathcal{A}$ and \mathcal{A} is a maximal consistent subset (i.e., a repair) of \mathcal{F} , it follows that $\text{Cl}_{\mathcal{R}}(\{\text{Con}(D), \alpha\})$ is \mathcal{R} -inconsistent, and D undercuts C . Suppose that $\text{Sup}(C)$ is consistent. By Lemma 1, $\text{Sup}(C) \not\prec \mathcal{A}$ since $\mathcal{A} \in \text{Repairs}(\mathcal{K}, >_*)$. By Definition 10 of the defeat relation, D defeats C , i.e., $(D, C) \in \text{Def}_{>}$. It follows that \mathcal{E} is a stable extension.

2. In the other direction, we prove $\text{Exts}(\mathcal{AF}_{>}) \subseteq \{\text{Args}(\mathcal{A}) \mid \mathcal{A} \in \text{Repairs}(\mathcal{K}, >_*)\}$. Suppose that $\mathcal{E} \in \text{Exts}(\mathcal{AF}_{>})$, we prove that there exists a repair \mathcal{A} such that $\mathcal{E} = \text{Args}(\mathcal{A})$. Suppose first that $\mathcal{A} = \text{Base}(\mathcal{E})$, and we prove \mathcal{A} is consistent. Assume for a contradiction that \mathcal{A} is inconsistent. Let $\{\beta_1, \dots, \beta_m\} = \mathcal{A}' \subseteq \mathcal{A}$ be an inconsistent set and every proper subset of it is consistent. Let $C \in \mathcal{E}$ be an argument such that $\beta_m \in \text{Sup}(C)$ and $C' : \mathcal{A}' \setminus \{\beta_m\} \rightarrow \beta_1 \wedge \dots \wedge \beta_{m-1}$. It follows that $\text{Cl}_{\mathcal{R}}(\{\text{Con}(C'), \beta_m\})$ is \mathcal{R} -inconsistent, then C' defeats C . Since \mathcal{E} is conflict free, then $C' \notin \mathcal{E}$; and since \mathcal{E} is also an admissible set, there is an argument $D \in \mathcal{E}$ such that $(D, C') \in \text{Def}_{>}$. Since D defeats C' , there exists $i \in \{1, \dots, m-1\}$ such that $\text{Cl}_{\mathcal{R}}(\{\text{Con}(D), \beta_i\})$ is \mathcal{R} -inconsistent and $D > C'$. Next, we will show D defeats an argument in \mathcal{E} . Since $\beta_i \in \text{Base}(\mathcal{E})$, there exists an argument $F \in \mathcal{E}$ s.t. $\beta_i \in \text{Sup}(F)$, which implies D defeats F . Obviously, C is attacked by C' but cannot be defended, which is in contradiction with the fact that \mathcal{E} is admissible. Hence, \mathcal{A} is consistent.

Now, we show that \mathcal{A} is maximal consistent, i.e., there is no $\mathcal{A}' \in \text{Repairs}(\mathcal{K}, >_*)$ s.t. $\mathcal{A}' > \mathcal{A}$. Assume the contrary. Since \mathcal{E} is a preferred extension, $\text{Args}(\mathcal{A}) \setminus \text{Args}(\mathcal{A}') \neq \emptyset$; and there exists $\Omega \subseteq \mathcal{A} \setminus \mathcal{A}'$ such that $D : \Omega \rightarrow \wedge \Omega \in \text{Args}(\mathcal{A})$. By the first part of the proof, $\text{Args}(\mathcal{A}')$ is a stable extension of $\mathcal{AF}_{>}$, it follows that there exists $\Phi \subseteq \mathcal{A}'$ such that $C : \Phi \rightarrow \wedge \Phi \in \text{Args}(\mathcal{A}')$ and C defeats D . Therefore, there must be an argument $F : \Gamma \rightarrow \wedge \Gamma \in \mathcal{E}$ (because \mathcal{E} is the preferred extension), and F defeats C . It follows that $\mathcal{A}' \not\prec \Gamma$. Moreover, observe that $\Gamma \subseteq \mathcal{A}$, then $\mathcal{A} > \Gamma$ (by the monotonicity). By transitivity, $\mathcal{A}' > \Gamma$ which is contradictory. Thus $\mathcal{A} \in \text{Repairs}(\mathcal{K}, >_*)$.

Dung [11] showed that the grounded extension is equal to the intersection of the preferred extensions. We next clarify the relation between the grounded extension and arguments generated by the intersection of all the repairs.

Proposition 2. (*Grounded Characterisation*) *Let $\mathcal{K}_{>}$ be a prioritized Datalog[#] KB with $(\mathcal{F}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{C})$, and let $\mathcal{AF}_{>} = (\text{Arg}_{>}, \text{Def}_{>})$ be the LAFP coresponding. Then the grounded extension of $\mathcal{AF}_{>}$ coincides with the intersection of the repairs of $\mathcal{K}_{>}$.*

Proof. Let \mathcal{G} be the grounded extension of $\mathcal{AF}_{>}$ and \mathcal{A} be the intersection of the repairs of $\mathcal{K}_{>}$. Let $\mathcal{A}' \in \text{Repairs}(\mathcal{K}, >_*)$ and $\mathcal{A} = \bigcap_{\mathcal{A}' \in \text{Repairs}(\mathcal{K}, >_*)} \mathcal{A}'$. By Proposition 1, \mathcal{A}' is a stable extension of $\mathcal{AF}_{>}$. Since every stable extension is also a complete extension, and \mathcal{G} is the minimal (w.r.t. set inclusion) complete

extension of $\mathcal{AF}_>$, it follows that $\mathcal{G} \subseteq \text{Args}(\mathcal{A}')$. Thus $\mathcal{G} \subseteq \text{Args}(\mathcal{A})$. In the other direction, let $\alpha \in \mathcal{A}$. Then there is no $\mathcal{C} \in \text{Conflicts}(\mathcal{K}_>)$ such that $\alpha \in \mathcal{C}$ (If $\alpha \in \mathcal{C}$, $\mathcal{C} \setminus \alpha$ would be \mathcal{R} -consistent and could be extended to a repair of $\mathcal{K}_>$ that would not contain α). Hence, there is no argument attacks the argument $D \in \text{Args}(\mathcal{A})$ where $\text{Sup}(D) = \alpha$. Since D has no attackers, then any extension trivially defends it, so D must be in \mathcal{G} . It follows that $\text{Args}(\mathcal{A}) \subseteq \mathcal{G}$.

Theorem 1. . Given a prioritized Datalog[±] KB $\mathcal{K}_>$, and the LAFP corresponding $\mathcal{AF}_>$, a query Q , and $\text{sem} \in \{\text{prf}, \text{stb}\}$. Then,

- $\mathcal{K}_> \models_{\text{AR}} Q$ iff $\mathcal{K}_> \models_{\text{stb}}^{\text{sc}} Q$ iff $\mathcal{K}_> \models_{\text{prf}}^{\text{sc}} Q$.
- $\mathcal{K}_> \models_{\text{BAR}} Q$ iff $\mathcal{K}_> \models_{\text{stb}}^{\text{cr}} Q$ iff $\mathcal{K}_> \models_{\text{prf}}^{\text{cr}} Q$.
- $\mathcal{K}_> \models_{\text{IAR}} Q$ iff $\mathcal{K}_> \models_{\text{grd}} Q$.

Proof. By Proposition 1 and 2, there exists a link between the set of preferred repairs on $\mathcal{K}_>$ and the set of extensions on $\mathcal{AF}_>$. Obviously, for every query Q and repair $\mathcal{A} \in \text{Repairs}(\mathcal{K}, >_*)$, it is the case that $\text{Cl}_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{A}) \models Q$ iff $\text{Cons}(\text{Args}(\mathcal{A})) \models Q$. The theorem is now proven as follows:

1. $\mathcal{K}_> \models_{\text{BAR}} Q$ iff for some $\mathcal{A} \in \text{Repairs}(\mathcal{K}, >_*)$, $\text{Cl}_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{A}) \models Q$ iff for some $\text{Args}(\mathcal{A}) \in \text{Exts}(\mathcal{AF}^>)$, $\text{Cons}(\text{Args}(\mathcal{A})) \models Q$ iff Q is credulously accepted.
2. $\mathcal{K}_> \models_{\text{AR}} Q$ iff for every $\mathcal{A}_i \in \text{Repairs}(\mathcal{K}, >_*)$, $\text{Cl}_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{A}_i) \models Q$ iff for every $\text{Args}(\mathcal{A}_i) \in \text{Exts}(\mathcal{AF}^>)$, $\text{Cons}(\text{Args}(\mathcal{A}_i)) \models Q$ iff Q is sceptically accepted.
3. $\mathcal{K}_> \models_{\text{IAR}} Q$ iff for every $\mathcal{A}_i \in \text{Repairs}(\mathcal{K}, >_*)$, $\text{Cl}_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{A}_i) \models Q$ iff for every $\text{Args}(\mathcal{A}_i) \in \text{Exts}(\mathcal{AF}^>)$, $\text{Cons}(\bigcap_{\text{Args}(\mathcal{A}_i) \in \text{Exts}(\mathcal{AF}^>)} \text{Args}(\mathcal{A}_i)) \models Q$ iff Q is accepted under grounded semantics.

This ends the proof of Theorem 1.

Example 2. Consider again the KB $\mathcal{K}_>^1 = \{\mathcal{R}_1, \mathcal{C}_1, \mathcal{F}_1\}$ from Example 1. The corresponding PAF $\mathcal{AF}_>^1 = (\text{Arg}_>, \text{Def}_>)$, in which the following arguments can be:

$$\begin{array}{lll}
 A_1 : \text{Advice}(\text{ann}, \text{bob}) & A_7 : A_1 \rightarrow \text{Prof}(\text{ann}) & \\
 A_2 : \text{AProf}(\text{ann}) & A_6 : A_2 \rightarrow \text{Prof}(\text{ann}) & \\
 A_4 : \text{FProf}(\text{ann}) & A_5 : A_4 \rightarrow \text{Prof}(\text{ann}) & \\
 A_0 : \text{Postdoc}(\text{ann}) & A_3 : \text{Lecturer}(\text{ann}) & A_8 : \text{Teach}(\text{ann}, c_1)
 \end{array}$$

The defeat relations among arguments are drawn in Figure 1. We have stable extensions: $\text{Exts}_{\text{stb/prf}}(\mathcal{AF}_>^1) = \{\mathcal{E}_1, \mathcal{E}_2\}$ where $\mathcal{E}_1 = \{A_1, A_2, A_3, A_6, A_7, A_8\}$, $\mathcal{E}_2 = \{A_1, A_3, A_4, A_5, A_7, A_8\}$; the grounded extension: $\text{Exts}_{\text{grd}}(\mathcal{AF}_>^1) = \{\{A_1, A_3, A_7, A_8\}\}$. Following Proposition 1, we have a correspondence between preferred repairs and preferred (resp. stable) extensions as follows:

$\mathcal{E}_1 = \text{Args}(\text{Advice}(\text{ann}, \text{bob}), \text{AProf}(\text{ann}), \text{Lecturer}(\text{ann}), \text{Teach}(\text{ann}, c_1))$,
 $\mathcal{E}_2 = \text{Args}(\text{Advice}(\text{ann}, \text{bob}), \text{FProf}(\text{ann}), \text{Lecturer}(\text{ann}), \text{Teach}(\text{ann}, c_1))$.

Evaluating our example queries yields: $Q_1(\text{ann}) = \text{Prof}(\text{ann})$ is sceptically accepted under the stable/preferred extensions (i.e., $\mathcal{K}_> \models_{\text{prf}}^{\text{sc}} \text{Prof}(\text{ann})$); $Q_3(\text{ann}) = \text{AProf}(\text{ann})$ is credulously accepted under the stable/preferred extensions (i.e., $\mathcal{K}_> \models_{\text{prf}}^{\text{cr}} \text{AProf}(\text{ann})$); $Q_2(\text{ann}) = \text{Lecturer}(\text{ann})$ is accepted under the grounded extension (i.e., $\mathcal{K}_> \models_{\text{grd}} \text{Lecturer}(\text{ann})$).

Fig. 1. $\mathcal{AF}_>^1$ Example 2

3.3 Basic Properties

Definition 11. (Rationality Postulates) Given a prioritized Datalog[±] KB $\mathcal{K}_>$, and the LAFP corresponding $\mathcal{AF}_>$. For every extension $\mathcal{E} \in \text{Exts}(\mathcal{AF}_>)$ and every argument $A \in \text{Arg}_{>}$,

- $\mathcal{AF}_>$ satisfies closure of extensions if $\text{Cons}(\mathcal{E}) = \text{Cl}_{\mathcal{R}}(\text{Cons}(\mathcal{E}))$.
- $\mathcal{AF}_>$ satisfies closure under subargument if $A \in \mathcal{E}$ then $\text{Subs}(A) \in \mathcal{E}$ (recall that $\text{Subs}(A)$ stands for sub-argument set of A).
- $\mathcal{AF}_>$ satisfies weak closure under subargument if $A \in \mathcal{E}$, $B \in \text{Subs}(A)$ and $A > B$ then $B \in \mathcal{E}$.
- $\mathcal{AF}_>$ satisfies consistency if $\text{Cons}(\mathcal{E})$ is consistent.
- $\mathcal{AF}_>$ satisfies exhaustiveness if $\text{Sup}(A) \cup \{\text{Con}(A)\} \subseteq \text{Cons}(\mathcal{E})$ then $A \in \mathcal{E}$.
- $\mathcal{AF}_>$ satisfies weak exhaustiveness if $\text{Sup}(A) \subseteq \bigcup_{B \in \mathcal{E}} \text{Sup}(B)$ then $A \in \mathcal{E}$.
- $\mathcal{AF}_>$ satisfies free precedence if $\text{Args}(\text{Free}(\mathcal{K})) \subseteq \mathcal{E}$ where $\text{Free}(\mathcal{K}) = \mathcal{F} \setminus \{\mathcal{C} \subseteq \mathcal{F} \mid \mathcal{C} \text{ is a minimal conflict}\}$.

Proposition 3. $\mathcal{AF}_>$ satisfies closure of extensions, weak closure under sub-argument, consistency, exhaustiveness, free precedence.

Proof. We prove each postulate:

Closure of extensions: We show that for every $\mathcal{E} \in \text{Exts}(\mathcal{AF}_>)$, $\text{Cons}(\mathcal{E}) = \text{Cl}_{\mathcal{R}}(\text{Cons}(\mathcal{E}))$. By the definition of $\text{Cl}_{\mathcal{R}}$, $\text{Cons}(\mathcal{E}) \subseteq \text{Cl}_{\mathcal{R}}(\text{Cons}(\mathcal{E}))$. In the other direction, we prove $\text{Cl}_{\mathcal{R}}(\text{Cons}(\mathcal{E})) \subseteq \text{Cons}(\mathcal{E})$. Let $\alpha \in \text{Cl}_{\mathcal{R}}(\text{Cons}(\mathcal{E}))$. Since \mathcal{E} is a preferred and stable extension, there exists a set of formulas \mathcal{A} such that $\mathcal{E} = \text{Args}(\mathcal{A})$ (by Proposition 1). Thus $\mathcal{E} = \text{Args}(\text{Base}(\mathcal{E}))$. Since the supports of the arguments of \mathcal{E} consist of the formulas in \mathcal{A} , $\alpha \in \text{Cl}_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{A})$. Hence, $\exists A \in \mathcal{E}$ such that $\text{Con}(A) = \alpha$.

Weak closure under sub-argument: Let $A \in \mathcal{E}$ and B be a sub-argument of A such that $B \in \mathcal{E}$ and $A > B$. Assume for a contradiction that $B \notin \mathcal{E}$. Since \mathcal{E} is a stable extension, there exists $C \in \mathcal{E}$ such that C defeats B which means $\exists \beta \in \text{Sup}(B)$ such that $\text{Cl}_{\mathcal{R}}(\{\text{Con}(C), \beta\})$ is \mathcal{R} -inconsistent and $B \not\prec C$. Additionally, since $B \in \text{Subs}(A)$ that means $\text{Sup}(B) \subseteq \text{Sup}(A)$, it follows that $\beta \in \text{Sup}(A)$. Hence, C undercut attacks A as well. Since $B \not\prec C$ and $A > B$, $A \not\prec C$. By the definition of defeat, C defeats A . It follows that \mathcal{E} is conflicting which is a contradiction.

Consistency: We prove that for $\mathcal{E} \in \text{Exts}(\mathcal{AF}_>)$, $\text{Cons}(\mathcal{E})$ is consistent. Let \mathcal{E} be a stable (preferred) extension of $\mathcal{AF}_>$. By Proposition 1, there is a repair $\mathcal{A} \in \text{Repairs}(\mathcal{K}, >_*)$ such that $\mathcal{E} = \text{Args}(\mathcal{A})$. Since $\text{Cons}(\mathcal{E}) = \text{Cl}_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{A})$ and \mathcal{A} is a repair, $\text{Cl}_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{A})$ is consistent. It follows that $\text{Cons}(\mathcal{E})$ is consistent.

Exhaustiveness: Assume for a contradiction that there is an argument $A \in \text{Arg}_{\mathcal{K}}$ such that $\text{Sup}(A) \cup \{\text{Con}(A)\} \subseteq \text{Cons}(\mathcal{E})$ and $A \notin \mathcal{E}$. Since \mathcal{E} is a stable extension, there exists an argument $B \in \mathcal{E}$ such that B defeats A . This means that there exists $\alpha \in \text{Sup}(A)$ such that $\text{Cl}_{\mathcal{R}}(\{\alpha, \text{Con}(B)\})$ is \mathcal{R} -inconsistent. We also know that $\text{Sup}(A) \subseteq \text{Cons}(\mathcal{E})$ and $\text{Con}(B) \in \text{Cons}(\mathcal{E})$. It follows that $\text{Cons}(\mathcal{E})$ is inconsistent. This contradicts the consistency postulate.

Free precedence: We have that $\text{Free}(\mathcal{K})$ is consistent with each consistent set of facts $\mathcal{F}' \subseteq \mathcal{F}$. Let $A \in \text{Args}_>$ such that $\text{Sup}(A) \subseteq \text{Free}(\mathcal{K})$. We prove A is not attacked. Assume for a contradiction that there exists $B \in \mathcal{AF}_>$ such that B defeats A . By the definition of defeat, there exists $\alpha \in \text{Sup}(A)$ such that $\text{Cl}_{\mathcal{R}}(\{\text{Con}(B), \alpha\})$ is \mathcal{R} -inconsistent. Hence $\text{Cl}_{\mathcal{R}}(\text{Sup}(B) \cup \text{Free}(\mathcal{K}))$ is inconsistent. Since $\text{Sup}(B)$ is consistent, it follows that $\text{Free}(\mathcal{K})$ is inconsistent, which contradicts our assumption. Hence A is not attacked and it is a member of every extension.

Now that we have translated prioritized Datalog[±] KBs to the LAFP. We also prove the use of argumentation as an explanation tool in our submitted paper. To show the applicability of our work in real-data applications, we will conduct an experiment with different datasets, and evaluate the experimentally result to show that our work provides more comprehensive and user-friendly explanations for query answers.

4 Application scenarios and discussion

To demonstrate whether our framework is viable, we conduct an implementation for benchmarks about the university domain and the biography domain. Note

that we select the Biographical dataset to show the LAFP framework applied to the case where the constraint for inconsistency is the equality-generating dependency. Note that the former approaches only considered the negative constraint, while this paper considered both two constraints (i.e., the negative constraint and the equality-generating dependency). Regarding *priority relations*, we construct priority relations by randomly assigning each fact a score between 1 and n for the example of the CQAPri benchmark. On the Biographical dataset, we build priority relations over facts based on the ranking of publishers. For each example implementation, we considered the following four cases: in Case 1, we focus on an explanation for certain answers; in Case 2, we compute an explanation for answers under grounded semantics; in Case 3, we consider an explanation for possible answers; in Case 4, we take into account a case where query answers are not accepted.

We implemented the framework in Java. In our setting, we made use of the Graph of Atom Dependency and the Graal Java Toolkit [5] to generate the new LAFP from KBs expressed in the DLGP format. Note that in the example implementations, KBs are firstly expressed in DL-Lite ontology or RDF, but not in Datalog[±]. Thus, we translated the KBs to Datalog[±] in the DLGP format, then encode them to the corresponding arguments. Rather than returning query answers under different semantics, our implementation provides visual explanations of the constructed argument and attacks as trees and pseudo dialogues generated from such trees.

The source code of the LAFP is available...

4.1 CQAPri benchmark

We reconsider a simple scenario in Example 1. The scenario is a part of the CQAPri benchmark. The CQAPri benchmark [8], a synthetic benchmark crafted to evaluate inconsistency-tolerant query answering over DL-Lite KBs, adapted from the LUBM₂₀³ benchmark. Figure 2 show the rules, the constraints, and the facts encoded in the DLGP format, and the corresponding arguments. We use queries in Table 1 to illustrate the practical interest of our explanation framework.

In Case 1, we consider $Q_1(\mathbf{ann}) = \mathbf{Prof}(\mathbf{ann})$ asking whether there **ann** is a professor. In this case, our implementation not only returns an answer for Q_1 but also provides the explanation formal for Q_1 and its graphical representation. For example, evidence supporting a certain answer for Q_1 includes **AProf(ann)**, **FProf(ann)** and **Advice(ann, bob)**. In spite of the fact that the evidence supporting the certain answer is invalidated by the fact *ann is a postdoc*, they are still defended by the fact *ann is a lecturer* since **Postdoc(ann)** is invalidated by the more reliable fact **Lecturer(ann)**. In the experiment, our explanation includes not only the facts deriving the answer but also the facts defending the answer against the conflicting facts.

In Case 2, we extend the above-discussed case in which the user asks whether "*ann is a lecturer*". Since we assume that **Lecturer(ann)** from the most reliable data source, there is no conflicting information to make **Lecturer(ann)** invalid.

Fig. 2. The GUI of our framework while carrying out a dialogue with a user

In Case 3, to discuss why a query answer is possible, we consider the case where a user asks whether `ann` is an associate professor. In this case, we provide an explanation for credulous acceptance accompanied with an explanation for credulous non-acceptance. The explanation as follows: $\text{AProf}(\text{ann})$ is accepted since the fact $\text{Lecturer}(\text{ann})$ defends $\text{AProf}(\text{ann})$ even though $\text{Postdoc}(\text{ann})$ invalidates it. Also, the answer is not an answer since $\text{AProf}(\text{ann})$ is invalidated by $\text{Postdoc}(\text{ann})$. Based on both explanations, we would claim that the answer for the query $Q_3(\text{ann}) = \text{AProf}(\text{ann})$ is the possible answer.

In Case 4, in the context of explaining why query answers are not accepted, we discuss the following scenario: An user queries whether `ann` is a postdoc. The answer is *No* since the fact "*ann is a postdoc*" is invalidated by the more reliable fact "*ann is a lecturer*".

Queries	
$Q_1(\text{ann}) = \text{Prof}(\text{ann})$	Is ann a professor?
$Q_2(\text{ann}) = \text{Lecturer}(\text{ann})$	Is ann a lecturer?
$Q_3(\text{ann}) = \text{AProf}(\text{ann})$	Is ann an associate professor?
$Q_4(\text{ann}) = \text{Postdoc}(\text{ann})$	Is ann a postdoc?

Table 1. Queries used in experiments.

4.2 Biographical dataset

The Biographical dataset contains data about... The original data is described in RDF format (<http://data.biographynet.nl/rdf>). We first use Protege to build an ontology that expresses rules and constraints, then the ontology is translated to Datalog[±]. All details are provided in Figure 3. For the dataset in RDF format, we use RDF-API package³ to translate RDF to facts of Datalog[±]. The conflict graph contains 192,028 facts (% of the facts are in some conflict) and 219,854 conflicts. Each of the conflict graph facts is in conflict with between 1 and 9 facts.

Rules
$bio : proxyIn(X_3, X_0), bio : PersonDes(X_3) \rightarrow bio : BioDes(X_0)$
$bio : PersonDes(X_3), bio : proxyFor(X_3, X_0) \rightarrow bio : PersonID(X_0)$
$bio : publish(X_3, X_0), bio : FileDes(X_3) \rightarrow bio : Publisher(X_0)$
$bio : BioDes(X_3), bio : hasFileDes(X_3, X_0) \rightarrow bio : FileDes(X_0)$
$bio : ref(X_0, X_3) \rightarrow bio : Publisher(X_0)$
$bio : hasDeathPlace(X_0, X_3) \rightarrow bio : PersonDes(X_0)$
$bio : name(X_0, X_3) \rightarrow bio : Publisher(X_0)$
$bio : hasBirthPlace(X_0, X_3) \rightarrow bio : PersonDes(X_0)$
$bio : hasDeathday(X_0, X_3) \rightarrow bio : PersonDes(X_0)$
$bio : hasBirthday(X_0, X_3) \rightarrow bio : PersonDes(X_0)$
$bio : hasName(X_0, X_3) \rightarrow bio : PersonDes(X_0)$
Constraints
$bio : hasBirthday(X_0, X_2), bio : hasBirthday(X_0, X_1) \rightarrow X_1 = X_2$
$bio : hasDeathday(X_0, X_1), bio : hasDeathday(X_0, X_2) \rightarrow X_1 = X_2$
Queries
$Q_5(\text{Simonde Graaff}) = bio : hasName(da : PersonDes-54067548_04, \text{Simonde Graaff}),$ $bio : hasDeathday(da : PersonDes-54067548_04, 1953-01-22).$
$Q_6(\text{Dammerman Karel Willem}) = bio : hasName(da : PersonDes-5033990_06,$ $\text{Dammerman Karel Willem}), bio : hasBirthday(da : PersonDes-5033990_06, 1888-07-04).$

Fig. 3. Biographical dataset: rules, constraints and queries.

In the Biographical dataset, we consider scenarios as follows: An user might ask whether a Dutch entomologist *Dammerman Karel Willem* was born on 1888-07-04. However, there is the higher prioritized fact "*Dammerman Karel Willem was on 1885-07-04*", which is inconsistent with the query. In this context, we provide an explanation for non-acceptance. The explanation is modeled from The answer returned *No*, and an explanation for the query say that the fact "*Dammerman Karel Willem was on 1885-07-04*" invalidates the fact "*Dammerman Karel Willem was born on 1888-07-04*".

³ <https://jena.apache.org/>

5 Conclusion

The problem of explaining query answers in inconsistent prioritized KBs still remains a challenge. We aim to provide a generic and unifying framework in which we use argumentation as an explanation tool for explanations in the existential rules context. The use of argumentation as an explanation tool in query answering has been theoretically studied in another paper, we then focus on the initial step of the proposed framework, namely the translation of prioritized KBs into AFs. To do so, we propose a novel logic-based argumentation framework with preferences (LAFP). We also provide a theoretical analysis of the LAFP with respect to its syntax and its properties. Finally, we empirically study the applicability of our work in real-data applications. The experimental results indicate that our work provides more comprehensive explanations for query answers.

In future work, evaluating our explanation by probably using human evaluation could be a direction for future work. It would be interesting to analyze the computational complexity of computing the argument-based explanations both empirically and theoretically. Another promising research direction is the formal study of explanation strategies in which our framework tries to adapt the user's preferences about inconsistency resolution. We will investigate how strategies can be defined in our framework following the literature of game theory and argumentation dialogues.

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